

ROLE OF INFLUENCER MARKETING ON IMPULSIVE BUYING BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUNG CONSUMERS

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Abstract

This study explored the link between influencer marketing and impulsive buying among young consumers. Consumer behavior can be heavily influenced by influencers, especially as digital platforms grow more popular. A total of 204 respondents were surveyed using two standardized tools: the Buying Impulsive Scale and the Influencer Marketing Questionnaire (Alcantara et al., 2024). Besides examining demographic differences such as gender and marital status between Impulse buying behavior and Influencer marketing scores, statistical analysis was also performed to investigate these differences. The results showed that influencer marketing and impulsive buying behavior have a significant negative correlation. Impulse buying behavior scores were not related to gender, but Influencer marketing scores were notably higher for males. The marketing influencer explained an 9.6% variance on impulsive buying behavior. Overall, this study helps deepen the understanding of how demographic factors influence consumer behavior through digital marketing. These insights can help brands tailor their digital marketing strategies. The main implication of this study is to assist brands in customizing their marketing efforts. By understanding how influencer marketing affects impulsive buying across different groups, companies can develop more targeted and effective campaigns. This can lead to better customer engagement and increased sales.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing social media usage has transformed how brands engage with their audience, resulting in the widespread adoption of influencer marketing. This strategy involves working with influencers who have large followings on social media channels such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, allowing brands to reach and engage their target audiences effectively. Influencer marketing, in contrast to conventional promotional methods, emphasizes building trust and emotional connections, making it particularly effective among younger consumers (Freberg et al., 2011; Lou & Yuan, 2019).

Influencer Marketing

However, the growing influence of influencer marketing prompts an examination of its psychological impact, particularly regarding impulsive buying behavior. Impulsive buying refers to spontaneous, unplanned purchases triggered by emotional or situational factors (Rook, 1987). The growth of social media has transformed marketing strategies, with influencer marketing playing a key role in shaping the behavior of young consumers. Influencers boasting large online followings leverage their trust and relatability to promote products and services, often prompting their followers to make

impulsive purchases. The credibility of a source, encompassing knowledge, reliability, and appeal, plays a pivotal role in determining the effectiveness of influencer marketing. Ohanian (1990) explained that these attributes enhance the persuasiveness of marketing messages. Furthermore, discovered that influencers regarded as highly credible are more likely to drive impulsive purchases, particularly among young adults in the U.S (Smith & Anderson, 2021). Zhang et al. (2020) found that when influencers are both attractive and relatable, they forge a stronger emotional connection with their audience, potentially leading to increased impulsive buying among Chinese youth. The type of influencer also plays a role. pointed out those micro-influencers, even though they have fewer followers, often have a closer and more trusting bond with their audience. This connection can lead to higher chances of impulsive buying, especially among Gen Z on Instagram. The study indicates that the closeness of the connection linking influencers with their followers may be more important than the sheer number of followers (Fadhilah & Saputra, 2021).

Impulsive Buying

Young consumers are especially vulnerable to impulsive buying because of their constant exposure to digital media, which shapes their identities and social connections (Casaló et al, 2020). Frequent exposure to influencer content, combined with emotional triggers such as FOMO (fear of missing out) and the desire for social validation, significantly affects the buying behavior of young consumers (Pradhan et al., 2018). Repetition in influencer marketing further strengthens emotional connections with products, increasing the likelihood of impulsive purchases over time. The content strategies used by influencers have a strong impact on impulsive buying. Posts emphasizing visuals and lifestyle, particularly those featuring time-sensitive promotions or exclusive incentives, generate urgency that often results in immediate purchases (Kim & Johnson, 2019).

Lee and Watkins (2022) found that scarcity-based content in influencer posts increased impulsive buying among young consumers in South Korea. Also, social proof shown through likes, comments, and shares strengthens the effect of influencer marketing. The quantity as well as the quality of social

proof on short-form video platforms positively influences consumers' impulse buying. This suggests that engagement metrics act as signals of trust and popularity (Feng et al., 2025). Psychological factors help explain how influencer marketing leads to impulsive buying. Koay and Lim (2025) introduced the idea of wishful identification, where consumers want to be like influencers. Their study showed that the match between consumers and products directly affected impulse buying intentions, while the match between consumers and influencers only mattered when wishful identification was present. Parasocial relationships, which are one-sided emotional connections consumers form with influencers, also play a role. These relationships, combined with feelings of harmless envy and a close association between the brand and the influencer, increased purchase intentions. These findings highlight how the emotional ties consumers build with influencers can lead to impulsive purchases (Sharkasi & Rezakhah, 2023).

Cultural and demographic factors also influence how effective influencer marketing can be. In collectivist cultures, social conformity and community approval are strong motivators of impulsive buying. Patel and Singh (2021) found that in India, consumers tended to engage in impulsive purchases upon seeing influencers who aligned with local cultural values. Similarly, Lim et al. (2020) reported that Malaysian consumers' impulsive buying behavior was affected by societal norms and the desire for social acceptance. Gender differences also emerged. Hashem (2021) noted that women in Saudi Arabia showed higher levels of impulsive buying in response to influencer marketing, which was attributed to their greater engagement with social media and purchasing power. The platform where influencer marketing occurs also plays an important role. A research study on TikTok affected impulsive buying behavior among Generation Z in Jakarta. Their results showed that factors like entertainment, interaction, trendiness, and customization were key in shaping consumer behavior. Additionally, word-of-mouth and features specific to the platform added further influence (Alyaa et al., 2023).

Similarly, You et al. (2022) investigated how online convenience impacted Generation Z's impulsive buying. They found that both transactional

convenience and post-purchase convenience positively influenced cognitive and emotional attitudes, which in turn increased impulsive buying. The presence of social media influencers was also found to strengthen these effects. However, while influencer marketing can effectively increase sales, it also raises issues related to compulsive buying and financial well-being. Studies have reported cases of individuals, especially young consumers, engaging in excessive, impulsive buying due to exposure to influencer marketing. These behaviors were often driven by technological ease and persuasive strategies, leading to financial difficulties. These findings underscore the significance of ethical considerations within influencer marketing. Marketers as well as influencers must remain aware of the potential negative impacts of their promotions and should encourage responsible consumption. Furthermore, more research is required to examine how different cultural contexts and content strategies influence consumer behavior (You et al., 2022). In conclusion,

influencer marketing significantly influences impulsive buying behavior among young consumers. Factors like influencer credibility, content strategy, emotional identification, cultural norms, and platform characteristics all contribute to this effect. While influencer marketing can be a powerful tool for businesses.

Theoretical Background

This marketing influence behavior is explained by Social Cognitive Theory. Bandura (1986) proposed that people learn behaviors from watching others, especially those they admire. Influencers who receive positive feedback for promoting products consistently are more likely to imitate this behavior by impulsively purchasing similar items. A buyer's attitude and behavior in the online environment are affected by observational learning, modelling, and rewards linked to the influencer's lifestyle.

Figure 1
Theoretical Framework of the Study

Note: This figure illustrates how Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory can explain influenced marketing behavior. It is influencers whose behaviors capture consumers' attention, especially these behaviors are reinforced through likes, admiration, or collaborations with brands. Consumers then imitate these observed behaviors, which can lead to impulsive purchases. A person's motivation to engage

in overall behavior and perception of impulsive buying of customers. Consumer behavior is driven by motivation, which drives individuals to fulfil their needs. An increase in interest can lead to a greater likelihood of replicating the influencer's actions, eventually resulting in purchases.

Rationale

Social media platforms have grown increasingly popular in the digital age, making influencer marketing a vital promotional tactic. Since a large portion of social media users are under 35, young consumers are prime targets for campaigns aimed at influencing them. Research on impulsive buying has become a key focus in consumer behavior studies. Influencers often promote products in ways that appeal to followers' emotions and aspirations through social media. The desire to imitate the lifestyles and preferences of favourite influencers motivates young consumers to make impulsive purchases. A typical trait of impulse buying is spontaneity, emotional excitement, and a lack of pre-planning. Current research suggests that visual and narrative cues on social media can heighten emotional reactions, making young consumers especially vulnerable to unplanned purchases. Few studies have explored the links between trust and credibility, content style, and exposure frequency in impulsive buying. Examining how often influential content is seen and the attributes that affect it (such as credibility, reliability, and attractiveness) can provide valuable insights into effective marketing strategies and consumer well-being. The novelty of current study in its focus on the interaction between influencer marketing and consumer impulsivity in Pakistani context. This study examines the relationship between trust and credibility, content style, and exposure frequency to reveal new dimensions of consumer behavior, translating into marketing strategies that strike the right balance between effective marketing and over all perception and behavior.

Methods

Objectives

1. To examine the relationship between influencer marketing and impulsive buying behavior among young consumers.
2. To assess the gender-based differences of influencer marketing on impulsive buying behavior among young consumers.
3. To identify the role of influencer marketing appealing to young consumers.

Operational Definition

This study examines impulse buying behavior assessed with impulse buying tendency scoring system of Impulse Buying Scale (Rook & Fisher, 1995). The influencer marketing assessed through scoring system of influencer marketing questionnaire. It examines influence marketing activities, brand awareness, engagement, brand growth, and perception and behavior in general (Alcantara et al., 2024).

Research Design

This study uses a **quantitative, cross sectional research design**, aiming to explore the relationship, differences and role of influencer marketing and impulse buying behavior among young consumers. The design is intended to identify statistical association between variables (Creswell, 2014).

Participants

This study involved 79 males and 125 females. The target audience consists of young consumers between the ages of 18 and 30 who actively use social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants who fulfilled the inclusion criteria (Bougie, 2016). Social media platforms were used to recruit students, as well as university networks. It was determined that a sample size of approximately 150–200 participants was necessary to achieve statistical power and generalizability within the demographic (Hair et al., 2010).

Instrument

The data collection tool was a structured, self-administered online questionnaire consisting of three main sections. The first section gathered demographic information, including age, gender, educational qualification, and marital status. The second section featured impulse buying behavior questionnaires, measured using two standardized instruments: Impulse Buying Scale (9 items, 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) (Rook & Fisher, 1995). The Cronbach's alpha for this scale was .80, indicating excellent reliability. The second measure influencer marketing questionnaire was a 12-item (5-point Likert scale: 1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely) which assessed the influencer marketing activities, brand awareness and engagement, brand

growth impact, and overall perception and behavior (Alcantara et al., 2024). The Cronbach’s alpha for this questionnaire was .62, considered acceptable.

Procedure

A literature review was conducted to identify gaps in existing research and choose a questionnaire based on the study's variables. The variables were carefully defined to ensure precise measurement, and the questions were designed to reduce bias and improve response clarity. This method supports a thorough analysis of the research problem. The authors provided formal permission. The questionnaire was then distributed to participants, and data were

collected to align with the study's objectives. The responses were analysed to address the research gaps and verify the study’s findings. The ethical considerations were followed as per APA guidelines.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations were key to this study. A clear introduction and research objectives explained in the questionnaire. The survey was voluntary, and no personally identifiable information was collected. This data was collected strictly for research purposes and kept confidential. Participants' rights were protected, and ethical standards were met.

Figure 2
Conceptual Framework of the Study

Note: Figure 2 reveals framework illustrates the relationship between influencer marketing and impulsive buying behavior. Influencer marketing elements, brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior. On impulsive buying behaviour. This model emphasized the pathways through which influencer marketing impacts consumers’ decisions

Results

The data analysis was conducted using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). The purpose of descriptive statistics is to summarize demographic data and provide an overview of participants' characteristics, such as their mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions. The

correlation coefficient (r) of Pearson's correlation between influencer marketing exposure and impulse buying behavior was calculated using Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r). To test hypotheses 1 and 2, correlations were computed, and significance levels were set at p 0.05. To determine whether gender affects impulsive buying, an independent t-test analysis was performed according to hypothesis 3. For hypothesis 4 and 5 analysis of hierarchical multiple regression analysis was computed to determine the role of marketing influencer on impulse buying.

Descriptive Analysis

In the present study, 79 males (38.7%) and 125 females (61.3%) participated. The average age of the

participants in the study was 23.74, with a standard deviation of 6.59. Among the participants, 45 (22.1%) were FSc/A-level students, 123 (60.3%) were undergraduate students, and 36 (17.5%) were graduate students. The marital status of the respondents was 164 (80.4%) single, 30 (14.7%) married, five (2.45%) divorced, and five (2.45%) widowed.

Analysis of Pearson Correlation

H1: Influencer marketing has a significant positive relationship between on impulse buying behavior among young consumers.

H2: Influencer marketing has a significant positive relationship between on brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior among young consumers.

Table 1
Analysis of Pearson Correlation of Study Variables

Variables	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 Impulsive Buying Behavior	204	25.23	6.43	-	-.19**	-.24**	.13	-.18*	-.18*
2 Influencer Marketing	204	38.21	7.16		-	.79**	.48**	.75**	.45**
3 Marketing Activities	204	11.39	3.09			-	.11	.45**	.20**
4 Brand Awareness and Engagement	204	6.89	2.21				-	.16*	-.02
5 Impact of Brand Growth	204	5.57	2.43					-	.23**
6 Perception and Behavior	204	4.83	1.57						-

** .01 level (2-tailed), * .05 level (2-tailed)

Table 1 reveal the analysis of Pearson correlation between the study variables. There was a significant negative association between the buying impulsive behavior and the influencer marketing $r = -.19$ $p < 0.05$. Both variables are indicated negative in direction. There is positive relationship between influencer marketing with brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior. The overall perception and behavior also negative associated with impulsive buying behavior.

Analysis of Independent t-test

H3: There are no significant differences in influencer marketing in terms brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior of and impulsive buying among male and female young consumers.

Table 2
Gender based Mean differences on Study variables

Variables	Male (n=79)	Female (n=125)	t(202)	p	Cohen d
	M(SD)	M(SD)			
Impulsive Buying Behavior	24.26(6.13)	25.84(6.56)	-1.71	.71	
Influencer Marketing	30.08(6.32)	27.80(5.68)	2.67	.31	
Marketing Activities	12.13(3.22)	10.92(2.92)	2.78	.11	
Brand Awareness and Engagement	6.60 (1.97)	7.07(2.32)	-1.47	.07	
Impact of Brand Growth	6.35(2.61)	5.08(2.17)	3.76	.00	.53
Perception and Behavior	4.98(1.53)	4.73(1.59)	1.11	.72	

Table 2 reveals the analysis Independent sample t-tests of gender-based differences. There was insignificant difference of all study variables expect impact on brand growth. The impact of brand growth shows significant mean different for male ($M=6.35$, $SD=2.61$) and female $M=5.08$, $SD=2.17$, $t(202)=3.76$ $p < .001$, with $95\%CI (.61-1.94)$ and Cohen $d= .53$ shows medium effect size.

H4: The demographic variables in terms of age, gender, qualification and marital status are predicting impulsive buying behavior among young consumers.

H5: The combined effect of influencer marketing factors, brand awareness and engagement, brand growth, and brand perception significantly predicts the impulsive buying behavior of young consumers.

Hierarchical Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 3

Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Impulsive Buying Behavior

Variables	B	95 % CI		SE B	β	R ²
		LL	UL			
Step 1						
(Constant)	22.57***	17.94	27.20	2.35		.023
Age	-.058	-.21	.09	.08	-.06	
Gender	1.420	-.42	3.26	.93	1.42	
Qualification	.427	-1.14	1.99	.79	.43	
Marital Status	.693	-.48	1.87	.60	.69	
Step 2						
(Constant)	29.04***	22.87	35.21	3.12		.096***
Age	-.06	-.22	.09	.07	-.07	
Gender	.27	-1.59	2.12	.94	.02	
Qualification	.81	-.72	2.34	.78	.08	
Marital Status	.74	-.41	1.88	.58	.09	
Marketing Activities	-.42**	-.74	-.11	.16	-.20	
Brand Awareness	.45**	.05	.86	.21	.16	
Impact to Brand	-.19	-.61	.22	.21	-.07	
Perception and Behavior	-.52	-1.09	.06	.29	-.13	

Note: CI: Confidence Interval, LL: Lower Limit, & UL: Upper Limit. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .005$ R²: Amount of Variance Explain by IVS, ΔR^2 : Addition Variance On DV, B: Standardized Coefficient, β : Standardized Coefficient, SEB: Standard Error

Table 3 reveals the hierarchical regression analysis coefficients on step 1 revealed sociodemographic (age, qualifications, marital status, gender) $F(4, 199) = 1.15$ $p > .05$). Based on the findings, a .023 value of R² which indicated a 2.3 % variance explains. However, in the In step 2, the R² of .096 revealed, that the marketing influencer explained an 9.6% variance in impulsive buying behavior with $F(4, 199) = 2.58$, $p < .05$. According to the findings, However, in the step 2 marketing activities ($\beta = -.42$, $p < .05$) and

Brand Awareness ($\beta = .45$ $p < .05$) where a significant increase in R-Square is observed when factors of impulsive buying behavior.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between influencer marketing and consumer behavior among young consumers, as well as to investigate the influence of demographic factors such as gender and marital status. The findings provide meaningful insights into digital marketing strategies impact consumer behavior in the age of social media. First two hypotheses Influencer marketing has a significant positive relationship between on impulse buying behavior among young consumers and Influencer marketing has a significant

positive relationship between on brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior among young consumers. The Pearson correlation was analysis the relationship between the study variables. There was a significant positive association between the buying impulsive behavior and the influencer marketing. Both variables are indicated negative in direction. There is positive relationship between influencer marketing with brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior. This indicates that as exposure to influencer marketing increases, impulsive buying tendencies decrease. This finding is unexpected, as previous literature has generally reported a positive association between influencer marketing and impulsive purchases (Lim et al., 2017). The participants who are more frequently exposed to influencer content may become more critical or self-aware, recognizing the commercial intent behind such content and thus resisting impulsive decisions (Evans et al., 2017).

One possible explanation for this inverse relationship lies in **Source Credibility theory** (Ohanian, 1990), which suggests that individuals are more persuaded by communicators they perceive as more credible. If influencer content misses perceived credibility or seems overtly commercial, it may reduce its persuasive power and even evoke uncertainty. This aligns with **Lou and Yuan's (2019)** findings, which emphasize how perceived commercial intent and message credibility reduce trust and increase resistance. This shift reflects a growing public awareness of sponsored content and the persuasive nature of influencer marketing, making a more analytical and critical mindset in consumers, as proposed in dual-process models of decision-making.

The third hypothesis was there are no significant differences in influencer marketing in terms brand awareness and engagement, impact of brand growth, and perception and behavior of and impulsive buying among male and female young consumers. The study also examined gender differences in impulsive buying behavior and marketing influencer using an independent t-test. Results showed that the mean Impulsive buying behavior for males was not significantly different from that of females. Impact of brand growth showed significant differences between male and female with medium effect size. This

suggests that male participants in the sample engaged more with influencer marketing content. Interestingly, this finding contrasts with earlier studies that reported higher social media engagement among females indicating that platform preferences or content types may influence these gender-based differences. Interestingly, this finding contrasts with earlier studies that reported higher social media engagement among females (Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017). On explanation based on **social cognitive theory** (Bandura, 1986), which suggests that people learn behavior through observation and identification with role models. If male consumers identify more with influencers (tech, gaming), they may be more likely to engage with their content, not necessarily in an impulsive manner.

To analysis the role of marketing influencer and Impulsive buying behavior, multiple regression was computed. step 1 revealed sociodemographic (age, qualifications, marital status, gender). Based on the finding value of R^2 which indicated a 2.3 % variance explains. However, in the In step 2, the R^2 of reveal that the marketing influencer explained an 9.6% variance in impulsive behavior. According to the findings, However, in the step 2 marketing activities ($\beta=-.42, p<.0.05$) and Brand Awareness ($\beta=.45 p<.0.05$) where A significant increase in R-Square is observed when factors of impulsive behavior. This enhances the explanatory power and contributes significantly to predicting impulsive behavior. The R-squared, however, decreases when variables are removed, reducing the explanatory power. R-Square values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater explanatory power. The negative relationship between influencer marketing and impulsive buying challenges the commonly held assumption that such exposure leads to irrational or spontaneous purchasing behavior. It is possible that consumers are becoming more aware of sponsored content and are developing psychological resistance, relying on more analytical thinking before making purchases. This interpretation aligns with Lou and Yuan (2019) findings, which emphasize the role of message credibility and perceived commercial intent in shaping consumer trust.

The practical perspective, this research suggests that marketers should move from surface-level engagement, like only promoting sponsored products,

and focusing more on building authentic relationships with consumers. Consumers may not respond to influencer content in a purely impulsive manner if they detect overt persuasion behaviour shown by influencers.

Implications

Study findings have implications for marketing influencers & research studies. Influence marketing exposure and impulsive buying behavior exhibit a surprising negative correlation, suggesting that consumers, particularly young adults, may be becoming more critical and selective about engaging with influencer content. This may indicate a shift in consumer awareness, where audiences are no longer responding solely impulsively to promotional material, but instead are engaging in a more reflective assessment before making purchases. It highlights the importance of cultivating trust and authenticity rather than solely relying on promotional strategies for marketers. Overtly persuasive tactics are less effective than influencer marketing that prioritizes genuine content, sustainable brands, and transparent communication.

In addition, the significant gender difference in influencer marketing engagement, where males reported higher scores on the influencer marketing questionnaire, challenges the widely held assumption that females are more responsive to influencer-driven content. This finding suggests that marketing strategies should adopt a more inclusive approach, considering the specific platform and content preferences across genders. The observed differences related to marital status also point to the influence of life stage and lifestyle on consumers' responsiveness to digital marketing strategies. For researchers, these findings encourage further investigation into the psychological processes that may underlie consumer resistance or skepticism towards influencer content. The results bring attention to the potential moderating roles of critical thinking, message credibility, and perceived commercial intent in shaping the influence of social media marketing on consumer behaviour. Future studies would benefit from longitudinal or experimental designs to better determine causality, and from more demographically diverse samples to enhance the generalisability of findings. Overall, this study contributes to a more

nuanced understanding of the dynamics of influencer marketing, offering insight into how consumers navigate digital persuasion in increasingly mindful ways. Furthermore, males scored higher on the influencer marketing questionnaire than females, challenging the widely held belief that females are more responsive to influencer-driven content. The findings suggest that marketing strategies should take into account gender-specific platform and content preferences. Consumers' responsiveness to digital marketing strategies also differs by marital status and life stage. For researchers, these findings encourage further investigation into the psychological processes that may underlie consumer resistance or skepticism towards influencer content. The results bring attention to the potential moderating roles of critical thinking, message credibility, and perceived commercial intent in shaping the influence of social media marketing on consumer behaviour. Overall, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the dynamics of influencer marketing, offering insight into how consumers navigate digital persuasion in increasingly mindful ways.

Limitations

There are several important limitations to consider when interpreting the results of this study. Firstly, this study relied on self-report measures, which could have resulted in response bias. Instead of providing accurate answers, participants might have answered questions in a way that made them look better. Consequently, the results and the way the relationships between variables were presented may have been affected. It is important to note that the study used a cross-sectional design, which means that data were collected at only one point in time. This makes it impossible to draw causal conclusions. Influence marketing and impulsive buying were found to be related, but we cannot definitively determine which causes which. The results of future studies using experiments or collecting data over time will assist in gaining a better understanding of this issue. Furthermore, it is possible that the unequal number of participants in different groups (e.g., based on gender or marital status) made it more difficult to find differences between these subgroups, despite the fact that the sample size was sufficient. The result is that

any comparisons among groups should be viewed cautiously, as they may not completely reflect actual patterns in the larger population. Lastly, all participants in the study were young consumers, which limits how well the findings can be applied to people from other age groups. Since age can affect both media use and shopping behaviour, future research should include people from different age ranges to make the results more widely applicable.

Recommendations

This study has several limitations, which can be utilized to make recommendations for future research. In the first instance, future studies should employ experimental or longitudinal designs. It is possible to use these methods in order to understand whether influencing marketing leads to changes in impulsive buying behavior rather than merely showing that the two are related. A diverse group of participants should be included in future research. Considering the focus of this study was young consumers, including participants from different age groups, cultures, and backgrounds would be helpful in making the results more applicable to a wider population. Further studies could investigate the psychological factors that influence how people respond to influence marketing. Finally, future research should pay close attention to the differences between groups

Conclusion

According to this study, influencer marketing is associated with impulsive buying among young consumers. The results of our study showed a significant negative correlation between the two variables, suggesting that exposure to influence marketing may reduce impulsive buying behaviors. This was unexpected, as most previous research found a positive connection between influencer content and impulsive purchases. While gender differences in impulsive buying were not statistically significant, males scored significantly higher than females on the influencer marketing scale. This may reflect differences in how males and females engage with online content. Overall, our results suggest that consumers might be becoming more aware and critical of influencer content, which could reduce impulsive decisions. This challenges the idea that

influencer marketing always leads to impulsive behavior.

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